

Studies on Noise Pollution in Alibag Region - India

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ABSTRACT

The current study is aimed at assessing noise levels in Alibag , an holiday location and a small town near Mumbai, during a regional festival to celebrate Ganeshutsov. Noise levels were recorded at four different locations in Alibag region using a sound level meter on a normal non-festive day and on the day of the festival. The areas were Chendhare, Varsoli, Shribag, and Koliwada. Various noise pollution indices were calculated to assess noise levels. Leq, Lmax, Lmin, L10, L90, LNP (Noise Pollution Levels), and Noise Climate were calculated. Noise levels were seen to exceed the norms set by the Central Pollution Control Board of India at all the sites on festive days, with a conspicuous increase in noise levels. The Chendhare site matched the category of safe zone on festive and non-festive days, Varsoli site exhibited the low-to-moderate-risk zone category for the 4 pm, 5 pm, and 6 pm time slots for festive days, whereas it showed the category of high-risk zone for the all remaining time slots of festive days. The Koliwada site indicated a high risk on the festive day. On non-festive days, the Chendhare, Shribag, and Varsoli sites indicated safe zone, safe-to-low-risk zone, and safe-to-moderate-risk zone categories, respectively. Noise levels have never been monitored in this area by any agency.

KEY WORDS: Noise pollution, Alibag, noise pollution, festive and non-festive, Leq, Noise Climate.

INTRODUCTION

Noise Pollution has become a nuisance with the ever-increasing development and rise in population in any country. It has multiple sources and is fast becoming a major ecological concern, especially in urban areas. Alibag is a coastal town in the Konkan region well known for its beaches, clean water, and fresh, rejuvenating air. It is a subdivision in the Raigad district of Maharashtra, India and it has many serene and beautiful beaches, known for its calm weather and dense coconut groves. Apart from the beaches, there are many historical places and intricate temples. Like other places in Maharashtra, the Ganapati festival is celebrated with great zeal in the Alibag region. In view of the rapidly growing population and changed ways of celebrating festivals, Alibag is facing an increase in noise levels.

Noise pollution is defined as an unwanted sound that gets dumped into the environment, and it adversely affects the health of a person and produces ill effects in living and non-living things (Iyer B, 2021). The World Health Organization rates noise pollution as the third most hazardous environmental type of pollution (Khilman, 2004). In the current study, noise level fluctuations leading to risk of noise pollution as a consequence of festive celebrations are evaluated in terms of various noise pollution indices. Various components add to issues of high noise levels, including an expanding population and increasing commotion levels in a vehicle. (Joshi N, Mule, P., 2021). Noise from man-made sources has been increasing over the past hundred years, and noise during festivals, weddings, and other social gatherings is becoming an environmental hazard. The major reason for increased noise levels is from transport vehicles, firecrackers, and musical instruments like dhol-tasha, banjo, etc. These cause significant noise pollution. A

considerable increase in noise levels has been recorded on festive days compared to non-festive days in other studies in Mumbai and elsewhere in the country (Payal Rane, Ambika Joshi, and Nitesh Joshi, 2013; Mule Prachiti., et al,2014, CPCB,2019., Rajiv B. Hunashala and Yogesh B. Patil, 2012)

Noise imparts several effects on mental and physical health and results in disturbances in daily activities. It affects living as well as non-living things (Pawar, 2005). Noise might affect sleep and conversation and cause hearing loss; in addition to these effects, it also affects human judgment and performance (Kumar, 2011). Generally, high exposure to noise levels can cause annoyance, irritation, damage to the auditory system, a number of health-related effects like physiological and psychological disorders, difficulties in daily activities and performances, hypertension, and heart diseases (Canter, 1996). Along with other types of pollution, noise has become a hazard to quality of life (Davar, 2004). Various studies have revealed that noise levels in some of the Indian cities are higher than the standards prescribed by CPCB, Central Pollution Control Board, and MoEF, Ministry of Environment and Forest, Govt. of India (Naik, 1999; Mohan, 2000; Gupta, 2003; CPCB, 2012; Joshi, 2012; Mangalekar, 2012; Kumar, 2001). Several studies have been carried out in India on noise levels, noise climate, Leq, and Lmax (Nikhil Kumar et al, 2013; Chaudhary et.al, 2012).

The CPCB has notified air quality standards for noise, which has been included as an air pollutant. Realizing the need to control and regulate noise levels, the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India, has notified Standards and Guidelines for Noise Levels under Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986, known as Noise Pollution (Regulation & Control) Rules, 2000 as shown in Table 1. The objective of this study is to

assess the noise pollution levels, noise climate, *Leq*, *Lmax*, Noise Pollution Level Index, and Noise Climate in this area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Alibag is a coastal town and a municipal council in Raigad district. It is the headquarters of the Raigad district and is located about 120 km south of Mumbai. The current study was carried out at four different sites in Alibag, viz., Chendhare, Varsoli, Shribag, and Koliwada

Noise levels on non-festive days and on festive days were observed during the Ganesh festival. The main objective was to monitor and evaluate the fluctuating noise level at different sites of the study area.

Instrument Used

A sound level meter of Lutron Electronics (Model number: SL 4012) was used to monitor sound levels at all the sites mentioned above. The readings were measured in decibels, dB(A) unit, where A denotes the “A weighting” characteristic, which is simulated as “Human Ear Listing” response. The time weighting is adjusted to “Fast” by default. The sound level meter is provided with a high-sensitivity Bruel and Kjaer Prepolarized Condenser Microphone (Type 4226) at the top, and readings are generated on the horizontal display.

Sampling Methodology

While recording the noise levels, the sound level meter was placed at 1 to 1.2 m above the ground surface level and one meter away from the sound source. The microphone of the sound level meter was pointed towards the source of sound, and readings were noted down. To minimize the error, readings were taken continuously for 30 minutes at an interval of 2 minutes. The noise levels were recorded. The reading was taken from 5 pm to 9 pm, from 5 to 5.30 pm, 6 to 6.30 pm, 7 to 7.30 pm, 8 to 8.30 pm, and 9 to 9.30 pm. Leq was calculated using the following formula:

$$Leq, T = 10 \log_{10} \left[T \div \sum_{i=1}^n 10^{\frac{Li}{10}} \right]$$

Where Leq = noise levels observed in time interval T and n = nth duration of measurement (Saler, 2012).

Leq is the Equivalent Continuous Noise Level, and can be applied to any fluctuating noise level. It is that constant noise level that, over a given time, expends the same amount of energy as the fluctuating level over the same time period. (MPCB, 2005). The readings noted in fractions were rounded off to the nearest integer in the observation tables. To detect the actual rise in the noise level, a set of readings was taken on a normal non-festive day. To get a better understanding of noise range, the Noise Climate (NC) index (Pathak, 2008) was calculated using the following formula:

$NC = L10 - L90 \text{ dB (A)}$. Total annoyance caused by noise level was estimated using noise pollution level index (NP) (Ehrampoush, 2011) Where, NC is Noise Climate; L10 is the level of sound exceeding for 10% of total time of measurement or Peak Noise Level; L50 is the

level of sound exceeding for 50% of total time of measurement or Mean Sound Level; L90 is the level of sound exceeding 90% of the total time of measurement or the background or residual noise level; Lnp is the noise pollution level; t1 to tn are the actual limit of exposure at the corresponding noise levels, and T1 to Tn are the permissible limits of exposure at the corresponding noise levels (Rajiv B. Hunashal And Yogesh B. Patil,2012).

$LNP = Leq * 2.56d$ Where $LNP = Noise\ pollution\ level$, $Leq = equivalent\ noise\ level$, and $d = standard\ deviation$.

Goswami and Swain (2012) and Swain and Goswami (2014) monitored different noise indices (L10, L50, L90, Leq, NPL, NC) in 20 commercial banks of Cuttack. Statistical analysis was carried out to analyze the significant difference between a festive and a non-festive day.

RESULTS

The deviation of noise from its mean point and L10, L50, and L90 values are shown in Table 2 and Table 3 on festive and non-festive days, respectively. Table 4 and Table 5, show the equivalent noise (Leq), maximum noise (Lmax), and minimum noise (Lmin) recorded at all four sites at different time slots on festive and non-festive day, respectively. On a festive day, the fluctuation in noise was more in comparison to a non-festive day. On the festive day, the 9 pm time slot at Chendhare showed a decrease in the noise levels as compared to other slots in the same area. Sound levels on all other sites exceeded the permissible limit at all times. On the normal working day i.e. non-festive day, a sudden depletion in the noise levels was observed. The Chendhare site remained noiseless for all the time slots. Shribag site was the

noisiest, followed by Koliwada and Varsoli, at 87 dB(A) at 7 pm and 69 dB(A) at 5 pm in Shribag was the highest Leq, while 53 dB(A) at 9 pm and 42 dB(A) at Chendhare were the lowest Leq recorded on festive and non-festive days, respectively. The continuous monitoring showed a broad fluctuating range. Varsoli site showed acute fluctuation, followed by Koliwada, Shribag, and Chendhare. L10 and L90 are defined as peak and background sound levels over a certain measurement duration (Chowdhury, 2012). On festive and non-festive days, L10 values for the Chendhare, Varsoli, Shribag, and Koliwada sites differed by 5-10 dB(A), 20-27 dB(A), 19-20 dB(A), and 15-25 dB(A), respectively, whereas the range of fluctuation of L90 value for Chendhare, Varsoli, Shribag and Koliwada sites was 6-12 dB(A), 20-24 dB(A), 16-19 dB(A), and 27-33 dB(A), respectively. The highest standard deviation difference between festive and non-festive days was recorded at the Varsoli site, and the least deviation was seen at the Shribag site.

TABLES:

Table 1. Ambient permissible noise levels in India as prescribed by CPCB

Area code	Category	Limits in dB (A)	
		Day time	Night time
A	Industrial	75	70
B	Commercial	65	55
C	Residential	55	45

Source: CPCB, 2012

Table 2: Noise level Parameters on festive days in dB (A)

5:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	61	56	55	56
Varsoli	80	75	72	77
Shribag	81	77	72	76
Koliwada	82	79	76	78
6:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	60	59	56	56
Varsoli	82	78	74	77
Shribag	87	80	79	81
Koliwada	86	80	79	80
7:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	63	58	58	59
Varsoli	84	78	77	79
Shribag	88	85	78	82
Koliwada	85	80	79	80

8:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	60	57	57	57
Varsoli	89	85	78	85
Shribag	91	86	83	86
Koliwada	85	80	78	80
9:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	63	58	56	58
Varsoli	88	84	73	82
Shribag	89	85	82	85
Koliwada	85	84	80	83

Table 3: Noise level Parameters on Non -Festive day

5:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	51	44	39	44
Varsoli	56	51	51	54
Shribag	68	63	63	63
Koliwada	61	54	51	56
6:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	53	45	43	49
Varsoli	59	53	52	54
Shribag	72	67	57	96
Koliwada	63	57	54	57
7:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	52	45	45	46
Varsoli	60	54	52	55
Shribag	71	60	58	61
Koliwada	63	52	52	54

8:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	57	52	51	53
Varsoli	53	48	46	47
Shribag	66	58	57	59
Koliwada	60	55	52	55
9:00 PM				
Site	L10	L50	L90	Mean
Chendhare	46	40	66	41
Varsoli	70	62	58	62
Shribag	69	61	60	62
Koliwada	72	53	51	55

Table 4: Noise levels on festive days

	5:00 PM			6:00 PM			7:00 PM			8:00 PM			9:00 PM		
	Leq	Lmax	Lmin												
Chendhare	58	62	56	59	62	57	58	63	56	59	64	58	55	57	52
Varsoli	78	84	72	80	87	75	86	90	71	84	88	61	58	59	60
Shribag	81	87	79	85	87	71	87	92	81	86	89	80	84	89	78
Koliwada	81	88	79	81	88	79	81	86	78	84	87	79	86	86	77

Table 5: Noise levels on Non-Festive day

	5:00 PM			6:00 PM			7:00 PM			8:00 PM			9:00 PM		
	Leq	Lmax	Lmin												
Chendhare	46	56	46	49	58	45	53	61	52	43	50	38	42	46	38
Varsoli	55	63	52	54	61	51	49	56	46	65	72	58	52	56	44
Shribag	69	75	67	66	77	58	62	71	57	66	77	60	57	64	52
Koliwada	59	67	53	62	72	52	57	67	51	64	73	50	54	59	45

Table 6: Noise risk zone

Intensity of noise in dB (A)	Category of zones
< 66	safe
66.71	tolerable
71-76	low risk
76-81	moderate risk
81-86	high risk
>86	extremely high risk

(Banerjee,2009)

Table 7: Noise pollution level (NP) on Festive and Non-Festive days

Time	festive day Chendhare	festive day Varsoli	festive day Shribag	festive day Alibag beach	Non-festive day Chendhare	Non-festive day Varsoli	Non-festive day Shribag	Non-festive day Koliwada
5:00 PM	63.45	58.84	88.87	87.31	55.01	62.07	74.05	68.08
6:00 PM	63.54	88.23	96.83	87.16	57.42	55.23	78.92	73.84
7:00 PM	61.54	97.84	94.7	87.01	59.76	74.55	70.51	67.42
8:00 PM	65.18	103.93	91.83	89.44	52.01	62.30	75.36	82.05
9:00 PM	58.82	108.19	91.18	90.77	48.21	62.30	63.85	67.86

Table 8: Noise Climate (NC) Index of sampling points

Time	festive day Chendhare	Non-festive day Chendhare	festive day varsoli	Non-festive day varsoli	festive day Shribag	Non-festive day Shribag	Festive day Koliwada	Non-festive day Koliwada
5:00 PM	4.7	5.7	7.9	6.6	7.55	5.55	6.55	9.4
6:00 PM	5.1	7.25	8.9	8.3	10.35	13.1	6	10.55
7:00 PM	3.1	5.15	11.1	6.15	8.45	8.55	7	10.15
8:00 PM	6.55	9.75	17.05	11.8	7	9.3	6.55	21.15
9:00 PM	6.5	7.4	20	11.15	8.4	7.3	6.8	13.9

Figures:**Figure 1: Histogram showing Noise Climate values against Time****DISCUSSIONS**

As seen in Tables 2 and 3, various parameters such as L10, L50, and L90 were calculated for different locations on festive and non-festive days. Along with these, the noise levels were calculated, which showed values from the safe to low-risk zone when compared to the standard table in Table 6. On festive days, high and comparatively steady noise levels were recorded and analyzed using the noise pollution level index. Comparative analysis of noise using noise pollution level index indicated that Shribag is the noisiest site, while Chendhare is the least noisy site of the study area. The Shribag and Koliwada sites show moderate noise pollution and less fluctuation as compared to the Varsoli site. Equivalent noise levels of festive days were high when compared to the non-festive days on all sites, and the majority of time slots of all sites showed a high noise climate (NC) index on non-festive days. One of

the major reasons behind this is the wide fluctuation range of noise on non-festive days. According to different categories of noise risk zones (Banerjee, 2009), Leq values of all sites were assessed to find out the level of risk due to high noise levels. The Chendhare site indicated the category of safe zone on festive as well as non-festive days. The Varsoli site exhibited a low to moderate-risk zone category for levels at 5 pm, 6 pm, and 7 pm time slots for festive days, whereas for the remaining time slots of festive day it showed a high-risk zone. For the Shribag site, the festive daytime slot of 7 pm and 8 pm showed extremely high risk, while the rest of the slots showed risk categories between moderate and high. Koliwada site values represented a high risk on the festive day. On a non-festive day, the Varsoli, Shribag, and Koliwada sites indicated safe zone, safe-to-low-risk zone, and safe-to-moderate-risk zone categories, respectively. The Ganapati festival is one festival that is celebrated with great enthusiasm in all the areas of Alibag region. On the day of Anant Chaturdashi (the Last day of the Ganapati festival), the immersion procession, which involved the use of loudspeakers, banjos, and firecrackers, continued to create noise for hours, thus affecting the usual sound levels. The majority of people are often unaware of the consequences of noise pollution on human health and the environment. Hence, it is essential to create awareness amongst the community about the impacts of noise pollution. Restrictions from local governments, such as a defined time limit for procession, limitation on the use of loud musical instruments, can also help in controlling the noise pollution.

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